

Identification of patients with multimorbidity at greatest risk of readmission and death. Role of patient-related variables. A qualitative study

Analysis of the results of a nominal group of health professionals and a focus group of patients and caregivers

Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital

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1. Introduction

The *WHO World Report on Ageing and Health* calls for the development of health systems that ensure access to integrated services that focus on the needs of elderly people. One of the needs identified by elderly people is the provision of suitable home care. Nonetheless, elderly individuals often have declining functional status, together with multiple health problems, and this results in frequent disruption of home care arrangements, either due to hospital admissions for acute illnesses or worsening of preexisting conditions, admission to long-term care facilities as they cannot be cared for at home, or the need for end-of-life care. In many cases, the hospitalization of such patients is unavoidable. It is nevertheless our responsibility to identify patients at risk of readmission or death, given the economic costs associated with readmission for health systems, and the health costs for the patient. Their identification is important to guide the implementation of personalized preventive measures from patient education on their health problem and self-care to hospital discharge planning, structured visits, and coordination between levels of healthcare.

Predictive models for readmission in patients with multimorbidity have been developed. They have not, however, considered patient preferences or their social circumstances. On the other hand, several studies have found the probability of readmission to be associated with social factors.

We hypothesized that there are social and patient- and caregiver-related factors that lead to readmission and even to death that, to date, health systems have not managed to identify, and hence, have yet to be addressed.

2. Qualitative research

Qualitative methods have traditionally been used in social sciences, anthropology, psychology, and education sciences. The aim of using qualitative research is to improve our understanding of situations, interpret phenomena, and develop concepts in their natural context, placing emphasis on the meaning, experience, and opinions of participants. Therefore, it involves techniques that focus on subjective interpretations and personal experiences.

Qualitative research can help us better understand some issues related to the health sciences and healthcare services, from a structural point of view, as well as in relation to the organization of healthcare processes and interpretation of results. The analysis of this qualitative data can provide healthcare professionals with highly valuable information on how to improve various aspects of clinical practice in healthcare organizations. Information retrieved using qualitative methods help us anticipate problems and identify solutions to facilitate complex decision-making processes.

In this study, we used two qualitative research methods, namely, nominal group techniques and focus group interviews.

The nominal group technique:

The nominal group technique (1-3) aims to find solutions to a problem for which there **is no explicit or structured information** by asking experts or individuals affected by the problem to address it. A group of 10-15 experts are asked to brainstorm responses to a given question, and then classify and rank the ideas generated in order of importance by consensus among them.

The focus group interview:

This is a conversation among a small homogenous group (of 7 to 10 people), which has been carefully planned and designed to gather information on a specific topic, with a script that progresses from general to highly specific questions, in a permissive, non-threatening environment with a moderator who is responsible for encouraging participants to express their opinions freely. This type of group is particularly appropriate for research on health promotion and health service management.

3. Objectives

The main goal of this research is to build models to predict the risk of readmission and death in the early phase or transitional period after discharge (within 1 month after the index episode) up to 1 year. To this end, we performed a preliminary qualitative study, to identify the needs and expectations of patients and health professionals and then include them as variables that could be included in statistical models.

The **objectives of this qualitative study** were:

To identify new variables related to

related to the probability of readmission and/or death in the transitional period after discharge until 1 year after the index episode

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Sample characteristics

4.1.1. Nominal group participants:

- 2 social workers (Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital, Basurto Hospital)
- 2 internal medicine doctors (Santa Marina, Basurto Hospital)
- 2 liaison nurses (Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital, Basurto Hospital)
- 1 family doctor (Basurto Hospital)
- 2 emergency department doctors (Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital)
- 1 nurse (Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital)
- 1 head of the Geriatrics Department (Parc Salut del Mar)

4.1.2. Focus group participants: caregivers of patients with multimorbidity

Participants in the nominal group drew up a list of patients with multimorbidity and/or their caregivers who we contacted and invited to participate in the focus group. We explained to them the objective of the group and where and when (date and time) it was to be held (Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital). We held the meeting in the evening, seeking to maximize the participation of caregivers who were more likely to be working in the morning.

From a list of 19 patients, 2 had died by the time we tried to contact them by phone. After contacting the 17 other patients or their caregivers, 6 caregivers finally agreed to participate in the meeting. The family relationship between patients and these 6 caregivers was: children (3), spouse (1) and son-in-law (2)

4.2. Group procedures

4.2.1. Procedure of the nominal group

- The nominal group (in our case, composed of doctors, nurses, and social workers) consists of a meeting of a variable number of “key informants” (ideally from 10 to 15 people), who are asked a limited number of questions.
- The nominal group procedure for responding to each of the questions involves six steps
 1. Silent generation of ideas
 2. Round-robin recording of ideas
 3. Serial discussion of the ideas
 4. Individual (preliminary) voting to prioritize the ideas
 5. Discussion of the preliminary voting

6. Final voting

4.2.2. Procedure of the focus group

Our proposal for this group consisted of talking to caregivers about a series of questions we put forward during the meeting:

- In your opinion, what are the main factors that led to their (your relative[s]) hospital readmission?
- What could have been done to prevent the readmission? What would have been needed for this?
- Do you and your family believe that they were ready to go home (at the time of the previous hospital discharge)?
- What most worried them about when returning home? What were their concerns/fears?
- What most helped them when returning home? And least?
- After getting home, have they had any difficulties with the explanations they were given about medication, diet, or other types of care they were supposed to follow?
- Since discharge, have they received healthcare at home (from a doctor, nurse, etc.)? If so, to what extent have such visits helped them improve their self-care?
- Have they had any difficulties communicating with the professionals caring for them (doctors, nurses, etc.)? If so, what type of difficulties?
- Since hospital discharge, have they had transport difficulties attending appointments? If so, what type of difficulties?"
- Can they count on the help of other people (neighbors, other relatives)? Who helps them the most? How do they help them?/What does this help involve?
- How important is the help of these people to their recovery?
- What other things help them stay at home, without needing to be readmitted?
- Is there anything else you would like to mention that we haven't discussed and that you think has influenced their hospital readmissions?

All the groups were held in the meeting room at Galdakao-Usansolo Hospital and were guided by health professionals with training in qualitative research. The meetings lasted approximately 2 hours and were audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed to facilitate the analysis, with consent from the participants.

5. Results of the nominal group with health professionals. Main factors associated with readmission

5.1.1. patient-related factors

- Lack of self-efficacy for decision-making
- Dependent patients being moved between homes, and hence, having frequent changes in caregiver
- Illness denial: still living like a person without MCCs
- Refusal to self-care and self-manage their conditions
- Age
- Lack of family and social support
- Cognitive capacity for self-care
- Patient who is also a caregiver
- Functional decline (primary caregiver gives up)
- Lack of a primary caregiver
- Living alone: frail patients who -on returning home- need a caregiver and end up being readmitted
- Difficulties with self-care at home (caregiver giving up)
- Poor treatment adherence and treatment discontinuation
- Lack of support for medication administration
- Non-adherence to pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments
- Patient level of independence
- Failure to adhere to dietary and fluid restrictions (alcohol)
- Lack of self-care awareness (daily weighing ... poor self-efficacy for self-care)
- Self-neglect in hygiene

5.1.2. caregiver-related factors:

- Lack of a primary caregiver
- Caregiver lack of self-efficacy for decision-making
- Functional decline (primary caregiver gives up)
- Advanced age: some caregivers are over 90 years old
- Change in family caregiver between readmissions
- Willingness and skills of the primary caregiver (not only for managing medications but also for following other instructions on diet, physical activity, etc.)
- Overload
- Lack of clarity over which caregiver is in charge of medication
- Stress
- Family members giving up

5.1.3. Patient medical factors:

- Drug adverse effects (adherence, interactions)
- Adjustment disorders with anxiety and depression
- Delirium (not resolved during admission, family giving up)
- Sensory impairment
- Poorly controlled symptoms
- Dementia associated with MCCs
- Discontinuation of medications, with medication reconciliation during hospitalization and in primary care
- Avoidance of overtreatment
- Transitioning from a paternalistic approach in medical and nursing care to a more patient autonomy-centered model.

5.1.4. Factors related to medical and nursing staff and continuity of care:

- Scheduled visits to chronic patients prone to exacerbations (program to detect readmission or exacerbation, known to primary care nursing staff → such visits happen, but the program does not foster continuity of care in the hospital emergency department)
- Nurse access to a care management tool (NAIA Healthcare)
- Insufficient medical/nursing support during follow-up
- In the transfer from hospital to primary care, patients and families being able to contact a doctor in the first few hours after discharge (provision of a contact phone number, without which patients would likely end up in the emergency department)
- Access to an advanced practice nurse (APN), to improve understanding of the medication
- Access to a primary care doctor after discharge (2 or 3 days after discharge may be too late; the response to questions about medication should be immediate) and access to doctors/nurses in general to address concerns
- Role of nurse case managers (in primary care for patients identified as frequent attenders to avoid emergency department attendance)
- Continuity of care: roles, primary care ... contact number for questions
- Real continuity of care on discharge (inpatient to home care, risk of patients and their families being left in limbo for up to 10 days with no continuity after discharge)
- Continuity of care: addressing of questions, clarity of discharge plans, home check-ups
- Proactive doctor in primary care, making a phone call to this type of patient, or the doctor who discharges the patient, who is the last to have seen them, taking on this role.

5.1.5. Psychological factors:

- Level of stress/depression in patients and their relatives related to the admission
- Emotional impact of the current disease on how the patient and their relatives feel (level of anxiety, caregiver distress).
- Psychological care (independent individuals who stop being “self-sufficient”: a new situation that requires adaptation: stress, depression, fear, lack of self-efficacy, and patients who seek readmission to ensure that everything is okay; these are emotional rather than clinical concerns, and involve not only patients but also caregivers)
- Substance abuse
- Psychological stress, disease impact
- Denial of the situation
- Self-neglect
- Lack of self-efficacy
- Loneliness
- Inability to self-manage.

5.1.6. Social factors:

- Poor housing conditions and lack of infrastructure, Diogenes syndrome
- Poor social planning on discharge (family situation, no one undertaking to care for the patient)
- Poor hygiene and diet at home (patients with diabetes, ulcers, and the potential relationship between dietary intake and ulceration), loneliness often being an underlying factor
- Educational attainment and cultural capital of patients and their companions (when explanations are not understood, there is a need to adapt and personalize information)
- Living alone, with no relatives (elderly individuals, with no partner, children or friends)
- Lack of economic support
- Homeless people
- Family conflict issues
- Lack of social support, difficult social and family environment
- Assessment of current social situation on admission: social support (start to facilitate access to social resources during the first admission)
- Resources: economic, housing, diet
- Home support
- Coordination between hospital and local council social care (patients are discharged with a request for support pending resolution, and when readmitted, the problem has not yet been solved; time frames differ between settings: resources take longer to arrive; a plan that can be suggested from a ward may not be feasible from the emergency department).

5.1.7. communication-related factors:

- Better explanations, ensuring that patients/caregivers understand the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis (dementia and stroke are associated with communication problems)
- Treatment printed in extra-large font improves adherence
- Discharge plans: explanations, paying attention to wording
- Understanding of the treatment: personalized information
- Education on diagnosis and treatment/prognosis for patients and their families
- Patient education: to maintain function status during admission
- Lack of a clear discharge information sheet is problematic (e.g., what does “as needed” mean concerning medications, and what are the potential complications).

5.1.8. medication- and healthcare system-related factors:

- Poor monitoring of the treatment
- Medication reconciliation and adjustment (what patient is taking sometimes differs from what is documented in the Presbide electronic prescribing tool: confirm medications with patients and their relatives and deprescribe)
- Medication: adherence, deprescribing, reconciliation/adjustment
- Discharge to home environment unsuitable for convalescence: keep patients in hospital slightly longer until they can be transferred to a short-stay unit; or until they will be better cared for at home
- Early discharge from hospital
- Mid/long-term hospitalization is associated with readmissions
- Symptoms on discharge: persistent symptoms and their management
- Difficulties in the diagnosis on first admission
- Dietary modifications (e.g., in cases of recurrent aspiration)
- Lack of more post-discharge social and healthcare centers
- System for medication preparation through outpatient units or pharmacies

6. Nominal group conclusions: summary table

Factors related to:	
Patients	Age, level of dependence, denial, self-neglect in hygiene, loneliness, self-care, self-management
Caregivers	Age, overload, changes, stress, decline, family giving up
Patient medical signs and symptoms	Dementia, adverse effects
Medication	Adherence to pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments, prescription, adjustment, reconciliation
Discharge care plan	Explanations, paying attention to the wording, clarity, written in extra-large font, individualized discharge reports
Medical and nursing staff. Continuity of care:	Check-ups at home, point of contact for questions early after discharge, social care, clarity of discharge plans; proactive doctor in primary care; access to an APN; insufficient medical/nursing support during follow-up; scheduled visits to chronic patients who tend to experience exacerbations; continuity of care ensured on hospital discharge: ability to ask questions, clarity of discharge plans, home check-ups; patient and caregiver education.
Psychological factors:	Stress, psychological care, fear, lack of self-efficacy, substance abuse, disease impact, denial of the situation, self-neglect, inability to self-manage
Social factors:	Cultural capital, poor housing conditions, lack of infrastructure, lack of economic support, lack of social support, family conflict issues, poor hygiene and diet
Communication factors	Need for clear written instructions, and clear explanation of the discharge plan, paying attention to the wording and using of extra-large font, ensuring that the diagnosis, treatment and prognosis are understood. Education for patients and their relatives.
Medication and health system	Medication: adherence, deprescribing, adjustment/reconciliation: check medications with patients/families and deprescribe; early hospital discharge; discharge to home environment unsuitable for convalescence: keep patients in hospital slightly longer to ensure that subsequent care is better

7. Results of caregiver focus group

Summary of the focus group with caregivers of patients with MCCs

To minimize readmissions:

Discussion of biomedical factors:

- Medication
- Follow-up: closer from the primary care center
- The essential role of the APN
- Doctors need to understand the role and usefulness of the APN

Discussion of communication-related factors:

- Improvement of coordination between hospital-at-home and other services: e.g., the hospital-at-home clinicians wanted to do an extra test during their visit, to avoid needing to draw another blood sample later; the primary care doctor needed to request this, but could not work out how to do so through the computer system.
- Improvement of lines of communication; it would help to provide guidelines to patients/families on when to call the primary care doctor
- Doctor-patient relationship
- Knowing the warning signs and who to call (the APN having provided three contact numbers)

Discussion of social factors:

- Social support after hospital discharge
- Flexible work arrangements to help elderly relatives; accompanying them to the hospital or primary care center visits, or to collect test results, because nothing has been envisaged to allow this
- On-site geriatric day care centers at workplaces, such as in Galdakao Usansolo Hospital, just as there is child care at institutions such as the University of the Basque Country

Discussion of psychosocial factors:

- Psychological support for caregivers: if we learn to put things in perspective, it might take less of a toll; this matters because we have no way of letting off steam and the situation is not going to get better.

Discussion of logistic factors:

- Access for family members to the showers at Galdakao Usansolo Hospital
- Food at the hospital is not good enough
- The care provided in the GUH is very good: when patients attend the emergency department, they are not made to wait in a waiting room, they are taken straight to an examination room.

